
A STUDY OF ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN RELATION TO THEIR STUDY HABITS

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ABSTRACT

The present research aims at studying the relationship between the academic achievement of secondary school students in relation to their study habits. The current study earmarked 300 secondary school students. The data was analyzed statistically by using Pearson's coefficient of correlation and t-test. The research of the study concluded that study habits are positively and significantly correlated to academic achievements and also concluded that the study habits of male and female senior secondary school students have a significant effect on their academic achievements. Results of the study also revealed that female students have better study habits than male students and also concluded that senior secondary school students of day – schools have more academic achievements than the students of a residential school.

Keywords: Academic Achievement , Study Habits ,Secondary School Students

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INTRODUCTION

All educational institutes perform the functions of teaching and evaluating its students' achievements and progress. Beyond doubt, a teacher is responsible for the all round development and proper learning of the students but it is indispensable for the students to have the habit of self-study. No teacher can be effective unless his students have the adequate study habits and perform well in the field of academic achievements. It's important to have good study habits for students so that they don't fail to keep up when faced with more challenging and time-consuming readings, subject material, and exams. Study habits are

important as these increase confidence, proficiency, and self-respect of the students. These habits can also reduce anxiety and stress of the students. Good study habits can improve the ability of the students to learn and retain knowledge. Hence, herein lies the relationship between study habits of the students and their academic achievements. Ireoegbu (1992) defined academic achievement as the level of performance in school subjects as exhibited by an individual. Achievement is the end product of a learning experience (Osokoya, 1998). Busari (2000) defined academic achievement as generally regarded as the display of knowledge attained or skills developed in the school subject. Azikiwe (1998) defined the study habit as the adopted way and manner a student plans his private readings, after classroom learning so as to attain mastery of the subject. Study habit can be interpreted as a planned programme of subject matter mastery (Crow and Crow, 2008). Crede and Kuncel (2008) defined study habit as study routines, including, but not restricted to, frequency of studying sessions, review of material, self-testing, rehearsal of learned materials, and studying in a conducive environment.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Oluwatimilehin and Owoyele (2012) conducted a study on 300 students of 12 to 16 years age range from the six junior secondary schools (two schools from each of the three senatorial districts) to examine the relationship between study habits and academic achievement of students in core subjects at the junior secondary school students in Ondo State, Nigeria. The results of the study found that there was a low positive correlation between study habits and students' performance in English language, Mathematics and Science. Art had the highest correlations with study habits subscales as compared with other academic variables. It was also revealed that students did not devote enough time to their academic work. Verma (2016) conducted a study on 160 students of 9th class, 80 from government and 80 from private schools of Gangtok, East Sikkim, to study the relationship between academic achievement among high School students in relation to their study habits. The results of the study observed that there is significant relationship between study habits and academic achievement of sampled students and also concluded that the study habit has an impact on the academic achievement of the students and the academic achievement of the students having good and poor study habits differ significantly. Raino (2017) conducted a

study on 300 senior secondary students of 11th class and investigated the relation between academic achievements and study habits, self- concept and emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students. This study revealed that there is a significant relationship between the study habits and academic achievements of the students and self –concept also has a positive effect on academic achievements along with emotional intelligence. The study also found a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of school students. Suman (2017) conducted a study to find the relation between academic achievement and study habits among 500 secondary school students of 9th class in relation to their meta-cognitive skills, learning and thinking style. The findings of the study reported that all the three variables (Meta-cognitive Skills, Locality and Gender) have significant effect on academic achievement of school students. The study also revealed that meta-cognitive skills and locality; locality and gender have double interaction effect on the on academic achievement of school students whereas the double interaction effect of meta-cognitive skills and gender is insignificant, but meta-cognitive skills, locality and gender have a significant triple interaction effect. Tus, Rayo, Lubo and Cruz (2020) conducted a study on 126 students of Grade 11 senior high school students of a private school in Bulacan, Philippines to determine the relationship between study habits and the students' academic performance .The results of the study showed that the study habits of the students are at a relatively average level and there is no significant relationship between study habits and the students' academic performance. Jaferi, Aghaei and Khatony (2021) investigated the status of study habits and its relationship with academic achievement for which 380 medical sciences students in Kermanshah-Iran were taken as a sample for study. The study showed that the status of study habits in 81.3% of the students was at moderate level and a direct and significant relationship between study habits and academic achievement was found.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the relationship between the study habits and academic achievements of the senior secondary school students.
2. To study the relationship between the study habits and academic achievement of the senior secondary male school students.
3. To study the relationship between the study habits and academic achievement of the senior secondary female school students.

4. To compare the study habits of the senior secondary school students of day-schools and a residential school.
5. To compare the study habits of male and female senior secondary school students.
6. To compare the academic achievement of senior secondary school students of a residential school and day -schools.
7. To compare the academic achievement of male and female senior secondary school students.
8. To compare the academic achievements of senior secondary school students in relation to their study habits.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

1. There is no significant relationship between the study habits and academic achievements of the senior secondary school students.
2. There is no significant relationship between the study habits and academic achievements of the male senior secondary school students.
3. There is no significant relationship between the study habits and academic achievements of the female senior secondary school students.
4. There is no significant difference between the study habits of senior secondary school students of a day-school and a residential school.
5. There is no significant difference between the study habits of male and female senior secondary school students.
6. There is no significant difference between academic achievement of senior secondary school students of day school and a residential school.
7. There is no significant difference between academic achievements of male and female senior secondary school students.
8. There is no significant difference between academic achievements of senior secondary school students in relation to their study habits.

SAMPLE OF THE STUDY

In the present study, random sampling techniques will be employed. The sample will comprise 300 students of day-schools and one Jawahar Navodaya Vidyalaya from district Mohali. Out of 300 students, 150 were male students and 150 female students.

Figure 1:

Pictorial form of the sample

TOOLS USED

1. Palsane and Sharma Study Habits Inventory (PSSHI) developed by M. N. Palsane (Pune) and Saddhna Sharma (2006)
2. Scores and marks of students from the previous results of their classes as Academic achievement.

HYPOTHESIS 1

Hypothesis 1 states, “There is no significant relationship between the study habits and academic achievements of the senior secondary school students.” This hypothesis has been tested with the help of results entered in Table 1.

Table 1

Results showing coefficient of correlation between study habits and academic achievements of senior secondary school students: -

	N	Coefficient of Correlation 'r'
Academic achievement and Study Habits	300	.384**

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The above table shows that the obtained 'r' value between academic achievement and study habits of senior secondary school students is 0.384 which is higher at 0.01 level of significance. The positive coefficient of correlation reveals if there is increase in study habits, it will lead to increase in academic achievement too and vice versa. It means that study habits are positively and significantly correlated to academic achievements.

HYPOTHESIS 2

Hypothesis 2 states, "There is no significant relationship between the study habits and academic achievements of the male senior secondary school students." This hypothesis has been tested with the help of results entered in Table 2.

Table 2

Results showing coefficient of correlation between study habits and academic achievements of male senior secondary school students: -

	N(male)	Coefficient of Correlation 'r'
Academic achievement and Study Habits	150	.425**

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The above table shows that the obtained 'r' value between academic achievement and study habits of male senior secondary school students is 0.425 which is higher at 0.01 level of significance. It can be said that the study habits of male senior secondary school students have a significant effect on their academic achievements.

HYPOTHESIS 3

Hypothesis 3 states, "There is no significant relationship between the study habits and academic achievements of the female senior secondary school students." This hypothesis has been tested with the help of results entered in Table 3.

Table 3

Results showing coefficient of correlation between study habits and academic achievements of female senior secondary school students

	<i>N (Female)</i>	<i>Coefficient of correlation 'r'</i>
Academic Achievement and study habits	150	.203**

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level

The above table shows that the obtained 'r' value between academic achievement and study habits of female senior secondary school students is 0.203 which is higher at 0.01 level of significance. It can be said that the study habits of female senior secondary school students have a significant effect on their academic achievements.

HYPOTHESIS 4

Hypothesis 4 states, "There is no significant difference between the study habits of senior secondary school students of a day-school and a residential school." This hypothesis has been tested with the help of results entered in Table 4.

Table 4

Results showing Mean, Standard Deviation, 't' value and level of significance of study habits of senior secondary school students of day schools and a residential school:

Variable	Type of school	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	Level of significance
Study Habits	Day- Schools	211	59.70	9.37	1.902	Not Significant
	Residential school	89	58.52	8.99		

The above table shows that it is clear that 't' value 1.902 was found not significant at 0.01 level of significance which indicates that study habits of senior secondary school students of Day- schools and a residential school did not differ significantly. So, it can be said that being a day school or a residential school has no significant difference on the study habits of the students.

HYPOTHESIS 5

Hypothesis 5 states, "There is no significant difference between the study habits of male and female senior secondary school students." This hypothesis has been tested with the help of results entered in Table 5.

Table 5

Results showing Mean, Standard Deviation, 't' value and level of significance of study habits of male and female senior secondary school students: -

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	Level of significance
Study Habits	Male	150	56.01	9.76	6.68	Significant at 0.01 Level
	Female	150	62.69	7.38		

From Table 5 , it is clear that 't' value 6.68 was found significant at 0.01 level of significance which indicates that study habits of male and female senior secondary school students differ significantly. So, it can be said that gender has a significant influence on the study habits of the students. In terms of mean score, it is observed that mean score of study habits of male senior secondary school students was 56.01 whereas mean score of study habits of female students was 62.69 which was higher than that of the male students. It can be concluded that female students have better study habits than male students.

HYPOTHESIS 6

Hypothesis 6 states, "There is no significant difference between academic achievement of senior secondary school students of day school and a residential school." This hypothesis has been tested with the help of results entered in Table 6.

Table 6

Results showing Mean, Standard Deviation, 't' value and level of significance of academic achievements of senior secondary school students of day school and a residential school: -

Variable	Type of school	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	Level of significance
Academic Achievement	Day- Schools	211	73.47	11.61	2.34	Significant at 0.05 Level
	Residential school	89	70.20	9.53		

From Table 6, it is clear that 't' value 2.34 was found significant at 0.05 level of significance which indicates that academic achievements of senior secondary school students of day-school and a residential school differ significantly. So, it can be said that it has a significant influence on the academic achievements of the students if they study in day – school or a residential school. In terms of mean score, it is observed that mean score of academic achievements of senior secondary school students of day- school was 73.47 whereas mean score of academic achievements of students of a residential school was 70.20 which was lower than that of the students of day- schools. It can be concluded that senior secondary school students of day – schools have more academic achievements than the students of a residential school.

HYPOTHESIS 7

Hypothesis 7 states, "There is no significant difference between academic achievements of male and female senior secondary school students." This hypothesis has been tested with the help of results entered in Table 7.

Table 7

Results showing Mean, Standard Deviation, 't' value and level of significance of academic achievements of male and female senior secondary school students: -

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	Level of significance
Male	150	70.21	11.91	3.639	Significant at level of 0.01
Female	150	74.79	9.77		

From Table 7, it is clear that 't' value 3.639 was found significant at 0.01 level of significance which indicates that academic achievements of male and female senior secondary school students differ significantly. So, it can be said that gender has a significant influence on the academic achievements of the students. In terms of mean score, it is observed that mean score of academic achievements of male senior secondary school students was 70.21 whereas mean score of academic achievements of female students was 74.79 which was higher than that of the male students. It can be concluded that female students score better in academics than male students.

HYPOTHESIS 8

Hypothesis 8 states, "There is no significant difference between academic achievements of senior secondary school students in relation to their study habits." This hypothesis has been tested with the help of results entered in Table 8.

Table 8

Results showing Mean, Standard Deviation, 't' value and level of significance of academic achievements of senior secondary school students: -

High/Low	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	Level of significance
Low	81	68.23	11.01	5.462	Significant at level of 0.01
High	81	77.58	10.78		

From Table 8 , it is clear that 't' value 5.462 was found significant at 0.01 level of significance which indicates that academic achievements of senior secondary school students in relation to their study habits differ significantly. It can be said that study habits have a significant influence on the academic achievements of the students. In terms of mean score, it is observed that mean score of academic achievements of senior secondary school students with low study habits was 68.23 whereas mean score of academic achievements of senior secondary school students with high study habits was 77.58 which was higher than that of the students with low study habits. It can be concluded that those students score better in academics that have better study habits than those students who have poor study habits.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

A purposeful research work always offers a scope for further investigation. A research cannot be considered worthwhile if it does not generate some of the important educational implications. It is anticipated that some of the findings of the present study may prove a wakeup call for all the stakeholders of the education system including the students also to improve the study habits of the students for getting better academic achievements. The findings of the present study on study habits correlates with previous research that found that students with good study habits perform better. On the basis of the finding of the present study, following suggestions and educational implications are given by the researcher: -

1. The present study proposes the integration of all subjects covering good study habits among the senior secondary school students.
2. Academic achievements are closely and considerably related to study habits; therefore it is crucial to design some tests to measure the study habits of the students.
3. Knowledge and awareness about the study habits of the students will help the teachers in understanding the weak areas and strengths of the students and to guide them more effectively.
4. The teachers should also conduct weekly, monthly tests, oral tests etc. and assess the students fairly which may be a stepping stone for improvement in study habits and as a result in academic achievement of the students because these tests will work as a motivation booster for the students.
5. Teachers can modify and improve their teaching strategies if they have knowledge and a better understanding of the study habits of the students.
6. All stakeholders, teachers, parents, governments etc, should endeavor collectively for the improvement of study habits of the students.
7. The efforts should be in the direction of cultivating the good study habits from the beginning, so that these habits will become a general behavior of the students at later stage.
8. Parents must be made aware that their contribution is important for the success of their children. They should create a congenial and friendly atmosphere at home which may prove to be catalyst for study habits and academic achievement.
9. Proper time table and provision of different curricular activities and innovation methods of teaching, use of educational technology also required in the school for improving achievement and study habits.
10. Some short – term courses or orientation courses may be arranged for the students about the cultivation of good study habits.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

The findings recorded in the present investigation are limited to study habits of senior secondary school students in Mohali district. This study opens a new avenue to research in the field of study habits to fill up the gap supposed by the investigator.

1. The study can be extended to other districts of Punjab.
2. This study is confined to senior secondary students. The same study can be conducted on elementary and high school students also.
3. Study habits may be measured using different tools and different dimensions may be taken into account.
4. The present study may be carried out on a larger sample. Sample size may be increased by including other variables.
5. Recommendations given by the researcher are that all stakeholders including lecturers, parents, counselors and the government should try to provide conditions to facilitate studying and improving study skills so that their academic achievement can be greatly improved.
6. Some programs should be created by the school personnel that will enhance the learners' study habits to improve their performance in the class.

CONCLUSIONS

The findings of the present study suggested that development of study habits will improve the academic achievement of students. There are many influencing factors in regard to study habits which include attitudes, personality traits, level of aspirations, subject matter, teaching strategies of the teachers, home environment etc. Hence, teachers and parents should endeavor to develop good study habits among students. Such habits are the best instrument for the students with which they can achieve their goals with confidence. The good habits, developed in the young age, definitely cherish the joy of its fruits in the rest of their lives. Generally, it is difficult to modify the behavior and habits at a mature age, so good habits must be developed from the beginning or from the primary level as the tender age of the

children is the best age to cultivate good study habits. Proper parental support and guidance can also enhance the academic achievement of senior secondary school students.

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